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PHARMACOGNOSTICAL AND PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS OF SHAWASAHARA DASHEMANI CHURNA

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ABSTRACT

Bronchial Asthma is a chronic inflammatory condition of the lung airways resulting in episodic airflow obstruction. The prevalence of Bronchial Asthma has increased continuously since the 1970s, and now affects an estimated 4 to 7% of the people worldwide. Ayurveda texts have described five types of Shwasa Roga and among these five, Tamaka is one. Tamaka Shwasa is a "Swatantra" Vyadhi. In Charaka Samhita, the group of ten drugs is mentioned for the management of the Shwasa Roga named as Shwasahara Dashemani. Till date no published data is available regarding evaluation of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna. Methods- Final product was subjected to Pharmacognostical and physico-chemical analysis such as microscopic study, loss on drying, ash value etc. Results- Pharmacognostical study showed the presence of contents such as; annular vessels of Shati, simple trichome of Tulsi, rosette crystal of Jivanti etc. Preliminary physico-chemical analysis showed that the loss on drying value was found to be 14.11%, pH 6.5, Ash value 7.80, etc. HPTLC showed 6 and 4 spots at 254nm and 366nm respectively. Conclusion- The pharmacognostical and physico-chemical analysis of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna confirmed the purity and genuineness of the drug. Further studies may be carried out on it on the basis of observation made and results of experimental studies.

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INTRODUCTION

Tamaka Shwasa is a "Swatantra" Vyadhi i.e. independent disease which having its own etiological factor, patho-physiology and management. It is mentioned as YasyaVyadhi i.e. a disease of chronic nature in Charaka Samhita, while Sushruta considered it as Krichchra Sadhya Vyadhi. Tamaka Shwasa is basically a disorder of Praanavaha Srotas while other Srotasas are also vitiated. The parallel disease entity in western medicine to this disorder is Bronchial Asthma. Bronchial Asthma is a chronic inflammatory condition of the lung airways resulting in episodic airflow obstruction. The prevalence of Bronchial Asthma an estimated 4 to 7% of the people worldwide.ⁱ As stated by W.H.O, 100–150 million of global population are suffering from Bronchial Asthma, out of which 1/10th are Indians and the prevalence of asthma is increasing everywhere. It is one of the most important chronic conditions causing elementary school absenteeism in childhood.^{ii,iii} In Charaka Samhita, the group of ten drugs is mentioned for the management of the Shwasa Roga named as Shwasahara Dashemani.^{iv} (Table 1) In the present day practice, among these ten drugs most of the drugs are being used in different combinations. But, no any research work or documentation is available about the use and efficacy of Shwasahara Dashemani as a whole in the management of the Tamaka Shwasain children. It prevent the attack of asthma due to anti tussive, anti inflammatory, mucolytic property etc. which is very useful to decrease the asthma prevalence. In the present study, the formulation is subjected to Pharmacognostical and pharmaceutical analysis. Preliminary organoleptic features and results of microscopy were verified and all the ingredients were proved to be authentic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection, Identification and Authentication of raw drugs

The raw materials were collected from the pharmacy of Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar. All the raw drugs were identified and authenticated in the Pharmacognosy Department, Institute for Post Graduate Teaching and Research in Ayurveda, Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar.

Preparation of the drug

As specific method of preparation is not mentioned for this drug, it was prepared in Pharmacy of Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar as per common guidelines described in classics and API for Churna formulation. Physico-chemical and qualitative analysis of the final product were carried out in the pharmaceutical chemistry laboratory of IPGT & RA, Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar under expert guidance.

Pharmacognostical study

The Pharmacognostical study comprises of organoleptic study and microscopic study of finished product scientifically studied at Pharmacognosy laboratory, I.P.G.T. & R.A., Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar, Gujarat, India

Microscopic Study-

Shwasahara Dashemani Churna was powdered and dissolved with water and microscopy of the sample was done without stain and after staining with Phloroglucinol + HCl. Microphotographs of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna was also taken under Corleisstrinocular microscope.

Organoleptic Study

The Organoleptic characters of Ayurvedic drugs are very important and give the general idea regarding the genuinity of the sample. Organoleptic parameters like Taste, Colour, odour and touch were scientifically studied.

Physico-chemical analysis

Shwasahara Dashemani Churna was analyzed using various standard physico-chemical parameters such as loss on drying, water soluble extract, alcohol soluble extract etc.^v

High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC)

HPTLC was performed as per the guideline provided by API. Methanolic extract of drug sample was used for the spotting. HPTLC was performed using Toluene+ Ethylacetate + Acetic acid (7:2:1) solvent system and observed under visible light. The colour and Rf values of resolved spots were noted.^{vi}

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organoleptic characters of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna

Organoleptic characters contents of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna like colour, taste, touch, Odour were recorded and shown in Table- 2.

Microscopic Study

Diagnostic characters of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna under the microscope showed annular vessels of Shati, simple trichome of Tulsi Rosette crystal of Jivanti, starch grain of Shati tannin content of Agaru Starch grain of Jivanti, pitted vessels of Tulsi etc. All these are showed in Plate no 1.

PHARMACEUTICAL EVALUATION

Physico-chemical analysis

Physico-chemical analysis of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna revealed the value of loss on drying was 14.11%, Ash value 7.807% w/w, water soluble extraction 17.38% Alcohol soluble extraction 5.75%, pH Value 6.5 are shown in Table –3.

HPTLC Study

The chromatographic study (HPTLC) was carried out under 254 and 366 nm UV to establish fingerprinting profile. It showed 6 spots at 254 nm and 4spots at 366 nm with Rf values were recorded which may be responsible for expression of its pharmacological and clinical actions. Plate 2, Table – 4.

CONCLUSION

Quality control of Herbo- mineral formulation is very much necessary to assess its safety, purity and universal acceptability. Standardization is a measurement for ensuring the quality control enabling the reproducibility of the formulation. The pharmacognostical and physico chemical analysis of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna confirmed the purity and genuinity of the drug. Further studies may be carried out on it on the basis of observation made and results of experimental studies. This study may be beneficial for future researchers and can be used as a reference standard in the further quality control researchers

Table1. Contents of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna.

Sr. No.	Drug name	Scientific name	Part used/Shushka	Ratio
1	Shati	Hedychiumspicatum.Hamexsmith	Shushkakand	1 part
2	Pushkaramool	Inularacemosa. Hook. F	Moola	1 part
3	Amlavetasa	Rheum emodi. Wall	Patra , Bija	1 part
4	Ela	ElettariacardamomumMaton	Phala	1 part
5	Hingu	Ferula narthexBoiss	Niryasa	1 part
6	Agaru	AcquilariaagallochaRoxb.	Kashtha	1 part
7	Sursa	Ocimum sanctum Linn.	Panchanga	1 part
8	Tamalaki	Phylenthusniruri Linn.	Panchanga	1 part
9	Jivanti	Laptidinia reticulate W & R	Panchanga	1 part
10	Chanda	Angelica glaucaEdgw.	Moola	1 part

Table2. Organoleptic parameters of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna.

Serial no.	Character	Observed
1	Colour	Light Brown
2	Odour	Bitter smell
3	Taste	Bitter
4	Touch	Fine course

Table3. Physico-chemical analysis of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna.

Serial no.	Test	Result
1	Loss on drying	14.11% w/w
2	Ash value	7.807% w/w
3	Water soluble extract	17.38% w/w
4	Alcohol soluble extract	5.75% w/w
5	pH	6.5

Table 4: HPTLC Study of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna.

Wave Length	Number of spots	Rf values
254nm	6	0.02, 0.46, 0.72, 0.79, 0.85, 0.98,
366nm	4	0.02, 0.73, 0.79, 0.94

Plate no 1- Microphotographs of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna.

Shwasahara Dashemani Churna

Annular vessels of Shati

Simple trichome of Tulsi

Rosette crystal of Jivanti

Tanin content of agar

Black debris of ofela

Scleriform vessels of puskarmoola

Pitted vessels of Bhuamalaki

Annular and spiral vessels of Amlavetasa

Brown content of Amlavetasa

Cork cell of Puskarmoola

Lignified fibres of Tulsi

Plate 2: Densitogram of Shwasahara Dashemani Churna at 254 nm and 366 nm.

254nm

366nm

Plate 3: Three dimensional HPTLC (3D) Densitogram

Abbreviations

- C. S. : Charaka Samhita
- W. H. O. : World Health Organization
- HPTLC : High performance thin layer Chromatography

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REFERENCES

1. International study of Bronchial Asthma and allergies in childhood (ISAAC). *Worldwide variations in the prevalence of Bronchial Asthma symptoms*, EurRespir J 1998; 12:315-35
2. Shah JR, AMDEKA YK, Mathur RS. *Nationwide variation in prevalence of bronchial asthma* – (part of the international study of Bronchial Asthma and allergies in childhood (ISAAC). Indian J Med Sci 2000;54:213
3. Gürkan F, Ece A, Haspolat K, Derman O, Bosnak M, *Predictors for multiple hospital admissions in children with Bronchial Asthma*, Can Respir J 2000;7:163–6.
4. CharakaSamhitaSootrasthana 4/37 Page No. 34 EditorYadavjiTrikamji Acharya, Publisher Chaukhambhaorientalia Varanasi Reprint 2011.
5. Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India PDF-1, Govt. of India, Ministry of health and family welfare, Delhi, 2007; 5, appendix-2.2.9: 214.
6. Stahl E; Thin-layer chromatography a laboratory hand book. 2nd edition. Springer-Verlag New York, 1969; 125-133.

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- International study of Bronchial Asthma and allergies in childhood (ISAAC). *Worldwide variations in the prevalence of Bronchial Asthma symptoms*, EurRespir J 1998; 12:315-35
- Shah JR, AMDEKA YK, Mathur RS. *Nationwide variation in prevalence of bronchial asthma* – (part of the international study of Bronchial Asthma and allergies in childhood (ISAAC). Indian J Med Sci 2000;54:213
- Gürkan F, Ece A, Haspolat K, Derman O, Bosnak M, *Predictors for multiple hospital admissions in children with Bronchial Asthma*, Can Respir J 2000;7:163–6.
- CharakaSamhitaSootrasthana 4/37 Page No. 34 EditorYadavjiTrikamji Acharya, Publisher Chaukhambhaorientalia Varanasi Reprint 2011.
- Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India PDF-1, Govt. of India, Ministry of health and family welfare, Delhi, 2007; 5, appendix-2.2.9: 214.
- Stahl E; *Thin-layer chromatography a laboratory hand book*. 2nd edition. Springer-Verlag New York, 1969; 125-133.